

CONTEXTUALISING MARGINALITY AND WOMEN - HOW DOES IT AFFECT THEIR HEALTH AND WELLBEING?

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Abstract

Marginalised – Who and Why?

Marginalisation is a process which pushes a group to the margins and accords them lesser importance than the others. This is predominantly a social phenomenon by which a minority or sub-group is excluded, and their needs are trivialised and ignored. Those marginalised have little or no control over their lives, thus, not on the opportunities and the resources available to them, either. This obstructs them in accessing resources, enhancing their capabilities and improving their lives, despite their labour contribution to society. There is a lack of a supportive environment due to which they are prevented from participating in community life, which often leads to their isolation. This vicious cycle has a tremendous impact not only on the development of certain human populations but also on the larger society, too.

The concept of marginality was first introduced by Robert Ezra Park (1928) and explained in an analysis of the causes and consequences of human migrations. He articulated that a “new type of personality” will emerge due to human migratory patterns during the late nineteenth and early twentieth century and would affect relations between population groups. Park's explanation was in the context of human movements demanding casting away some things (of the place of origin) and imbibing some other (of the place of destination), creating a new personality comprising of “cultural hybrid, ... a man on the margin of two cultures and two societies, which never completely interpenetrated and fused.” This idea of rigid compartmentalisation between those on the margins versus those in the core was further probed by Edwin Stonequist (1937) more extensively than Park. He highlighted the personality features of marginality and focused his critique into an assessment of the mental state of those marginalised.

Thus, Stonequist defined marginality beyond the differences between two cultures and societies which are associated with the migrant population. The travail and

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resentment experienced during assimilation and acceptance in the place of destination; and the gloom of letting go of all that symbolises the place of origin, was made an important factor for understanding this change in what Park called cultural hybridisation. Considering that most migration occurs in anticipation of improving the living conditions, it is also linked with the underprivileged and marginalised conditions in the place(s) of origin which act as push factors. Therefore, the present context of marginality is reflected through the Park–Stonequist model of marginality. It became the predominant model and a reference point for studies of marginality until Dickie-Clark (1966) introduced the term “marginal situation” and moved the discussion from the personality of the marginalised to a more pointedly sociological reference point (Dennis 1991). Dickie-Clark (1966) shifted the attention from the individual to the conditions which created barriers for groups of people in accessing resources for betterment. The thrust, however, remained on the people, rather than the conditions. Therefore, the Park–Stonequist model, is often critiqued for its lopsided explanation of marginality by subverting the sociological context (Denis, 2007). It has been well-documented that social identity and gender are stark markers of marginality. The present papers, therefore, endeavour to explore the factors responsible for the marginality of women and their access to healthcare. Using the lens of intersectionality, oppression and equity form the basis of the core argument which attempts to reflect on the marginalised women while examining the marginality of women. The term “Dalit” is being used in its literal context and, therefore, will include all women marginalised based on their social identity – caste, ethnicity, and religion.

In this backdrop, therefore, to understand women's health, it is important to re-examine the theoretical underpinnings, particularly of the women's health movement.

Deconstructing Knowledge and the Knower in Context of Women and their Health:

The scope of health research goes beyond genetic, and physiological differences. The concurrent explanations regarding structural and hierarchical norms of race, gender, geography, socioeconomic status, and caste in the context of the Indian sub-continent impact access to resources, knowledge and service. They become an essential mechanism to take the discourse further. This also essentialises acknowledging opportunities for women's health knowledge; both as consumers and as producers. However, as evident, in the context of women, the thrust remains more on consumption rather than production of knowledge. This inevitably demarcates the ‘knower’ (non-women) and the ‘non-knower’ (women) and creates a divide between them. The increasing medicalisation of women's lives (Offman and

Kleinplatz, 2004, Lafrance, 2007) constraints women's reproductive choices (Gostin 2007) and in the process, strengthens this notion of women as 'non-knower'. In addition, orientation towards the pharmaceuticalisation of women's mental health (Metzl and Angel, 2004), is informed by ideology rather than evidence (Crane and Dusenberry, 2004), perpetuating the assumption of women as consumers only, and widening the divide.

Research needs to be anchored in epistemology. In the context of women's health, particularly of those on the margins, the way knowledge, and the knower, is valued (or challenged) becomes an essential component of enquiry. The traditional ideas and knowledge is central to women's health and the movement around it. Therefore, epistemology must be prioritised in order to continue to benefit from this strong tradition of reflexive philosophical inquiry in women's health (Cook, 2007, 143). Women's health received the attention of the critical theorists who grew increasingly cognizant of the process and outcomes of oppressions associated with gender, race, class, caste, physical and mental ability status, and sexuality. However, their understanding was embedded in the assumption that all women share a set of common factors of oppression and discrimination (Cook, 2007).

The discourse on women's rights concerned itself with the differentials between the majority of sexual identities. From *Sexual Politics* (Millett, 1971), to the most celebrated *The Second Sex* (de Beauvoir, 1972), and *Reproducing Mothering* (Chodorow, 1978) of the 1970s, it continued through the next decade flourishing in the notion of sisterhood (Hooks, 1986) and the understanding of cultural feminism and post-structuralism (Alcoff, 1988). Towards the end of the 1980s, a discerning idea emerged from the work of Kimberley Crenshaw (1989). Her thesis laid the foundation of intersectionality discourse globally by demarginalising the intersection of race and sex. As the 1990s approached, gender dimension in the discourse gained prominence with reflections in the attempts to examine social-psychological model of gender (Deaux, and Major, 1990,) and family structure and feminine personality, (Chodorow, 1995), widening the discourse with the emphasis on understanding its genesis (COE, nd). In the process, it consolidated women as an entity of enquiry, giving way to the realms of intersectionality.

Women in their Heterogeneity:

The women's movement in India, after the Beijing conference, shaped itself through the mobilisation of women by feminist and political groups. But homogenisation of women led to the organisation of Dalit women separately. There are both internal and external factors that have a bearing on this phenomenon. The justification for talking differently rests on the external

factors (non-Dalit forces homogenising the issue of Dalit women) and internal factors (the patriarchal domination within the Dalits). However, external factors often remain inept in explaining the complex reality of Dalit women (Guru, 1995). For instance, the rape of a Dalit woman needs to be scrutinised in terms of class, criminality, psychopathic condition, perpetration of male violence, and most importantly, the caste factor. This makes sexual violence against Dalit (and tribal) women more severe in intensity and magnitude (Vivek Kumar, 2005).

Therefore, treating women as a homogenous group has yielded erroneous frameworks for any enquiry of them. Women as a homogenised group have hidden more than revealed the realities of women across social groups. The category of 'women' is in itself pluralistic. Thus, the discourse on women needs to be disaggregated by their social identity, keeping aside the fear of fracturing their 'unity' – as often alleged by feminist thinkers. Literature supports that there is a paradoxical inverse relationship between caste and gender in Indian society. Stringent patriarchal codes designed to subordinate women have been observed to be restricted to high-status caste groups; women from low-status castes display higher labour force participation rates, fewer patriarchal restrictions on mobility and greater decision-making autonomy (Boserup, 1970; Mencher, 1988; Chen, 1995; Kapadia, 1995; Eswaran et al., 2013).

A related argument is that increases in wealth and income among low-ranked castes can have a negative impact on the status of women: as these castes emulate the customs, practices, and patriarchal codes of higher-ranked castes, women become disempowered (Srinivas, 1977). While this needs to be tested in the changing times, we take pride in the 33 million women who are actively participating in the Self-Help Groups (SHGs). Additionally, there are 1.3 million women elected representatives in our panchayats. However, we also have 20,000 women committing suicide in 2014. In the same year, 5,650 farmers, too, killed themselves in the country. The number of suicides by women was about four times more than the farmers- significantly higher than that of farmers' suicides. These women comprised 47% of the total female victims. While the farmers' suicide got the deserved attention from all quarters media to state, forming a sizeable part of our country's developmental and political discourse, women's suicide went unnoticed despite its quantum (Biswas, 2016).

The discourse on women has traditionally focused on their reproductive role and therefore, their body. The focus on their economic role as a worker contributing to the GDP has got lesser importance; and thus, their contribution to the economic (and social) development process remained ignored till about recently.

Theoretical Framework:

In the dichotomous framework of inequality and oppression, the diversity, equity, and inclusion (DEI) theory of change enables us to understand racism and other forms of social identity-based oppression such as caste in the South Asian context. Operating at the intra/interpersonal, organisational, and structural levels, comprising historical, economic, political, social, and cultural factors, change at every level becomes critical in achieving equity (Cook, 1997, Cook et al., 2022) including health. Therefore, intersectionality, relational-cultural theory, and critical consciousness become essential to inform and evaluate the social and cultural environment; and understand the consequent change. Thus, advancing health equity requires fostering a culture of equity (Chin, et al., 2012). Relational-cultural theory explains that culture is represented as well as reproduced (Baily et al., 2017) and therefore influences health.

The historically-grounded intersecting systems of oppression shape lived experiences related to health care through differences in access and provision of care services, for instance, during childbirth for women of different hues–ethnicity, minority status, ability status, regional identity with different levels of education and immigration histories (Collins, 1999; The NAS, 2019) and caste in Indian sub-continent (Borooah, 2014). The care providers interact with care seekers and the community with their understanding of equity which is embedded in the social determinants of the health framework and can be used for improving the quality of care and eliminating disparities (Perry et al., 2014; The NAS, 2019). However, the care providers at the grassroots level have little power within the health system. Therefore, developing critical consciousness, the ability to analyse social conditions and engaging in individual or collective action to reduce inequities, providing a mechanism for change becomes essential (Perry et al., 2014). Therefore, intersectionality, relational-cultural theory, and critical consciousness together must be used to build a culture of equity.

While marginality underscores women as compared to men, marginalisation among women affects some more than others. Marginalisation can occur on a variety of axes. Some of them are educational attainment, income and wealth, living arrangement, age, ability status, marital status, health status, place of residence, ethnicity, and caste and religion. The intersection of ethnicity, caste and religion with other axes is important in carving out marginalisation among women. It is evident that rural residence marginalises women in terms of education examined through schooling, Gross Attendance Ratio (GAR) and Gender Parity Index (GPI); and media, for instance, as compared to women in urban areas. Similarly, religious identity also plays an important role in accentuating marginality as does caste/tribe identity. Muslims are most

marginalised as are the scheduled tribe (ST) women in access to schooling, GAR and GPI. Similarly, women in the lowest Wealth Quintile are most marginalised as compared to the women in other wealth quintiles. In contrast, those in the highest wealth quintile are the least marginalised (Table 1).

Table 1- Position of Women in Education and Media Exposure by Characteristics

Characteristics	No Schooling*	GAR+	GAR Gender Parity Index+	No regular exposure to any media++
Residence				
Urban	17.4	87.9	1.02	23.2
Rural	33.2	78.1	0.95	49.9
Religion				
Hindu	28.5	82.4	0.96	39.8
Muslim	29.1	71.0	1.00	52.7
Christian	17.9	88.6	1.02	29.9
Sikh	23.2	92.0	1.00	34.3
Buddhist/Neo Buddhist	22.7	97.2	1.06	33.4
Jain	4.8	94.7	1.02	11.4
Other	34.8	75.8	1.03	65.0
Caste/Tribe				
Scheduled Caste	32.6	78.3	0.96	43.4
Scheduled Tribe	38.5	73.8	0.96	56.1
Other Backward Class	28.8	81.2	0.96	40.3
Other	19.5	86.0	1.00	35.1
Don't Know	32.9	72.7	1.04	54.3
Wealth Quintile				
Lowest	45.7	65.8	0.97	78.5
Second	35.5	78.4	0.96	55.2
Middle	28.3	84.4	0.98	35.6
Fourth	20.0	88.8	0.98	24.9
Highest	11.4	94.7	0.98	15.7
Total	28.4	80.9	0.97	41.2
NFHS-4 (2015-16)	31.0			

Source:*Table 2.24 Educational Attainment of Household Population. Per cent distribution of the de facto female and male household populations age six and over by highest number of years of schooling completed and median number of years of schooling completed, according to selected background characteristics, India, 2019-21, and NFHS-4 Page 62

+Table 2.27 School attendance ratios [Middle, Secondary, And Higher Secondary School] Net attendance ratios (NAR), gross attendance ratios (GAR), and Gender Parity Index (GPI) for the de facto household population by level of schooling and sex, according to selected background characteristics, India, 2019-21

++Table 3.5.1 Exposure to mass media: Women Percentage of women aged 15-49 who usually read a newspaper or magazine, watch television, or listen to the radio at least once a week, who usually visit the cinema or theatre at least once a month, and who are not regularly exposed to any of these media by background characteristics, India, 2019-21

NOTE:

2 The GPI for primary school is the ratio of the primary school NAR (GAR) for females to the NAR (GAR) for males. The gender parity index for middle, secondary, and higher secondary school is the ratio of the NAR (GAR) for females to the NAR (GAR) for males at those levels of school.

3 The GAR for primary school (standards 1-5) is the total number of primary school students, expressed as a percentage of the official primary-school-age population (6-10 years). The GAR for middle, secondary, and higher secondary school (standards 6-12) is the total number of students in those school levels, expressed as a percentage of the official population that is the appropriate age to be attending those school levels. If there are significant numbers of overage and underage students at a given level of schooling, the GAR can exceed 100.0.

Dalit Women in Development Narrative:

The development narrative concentrates on gender parity and positions women evenly across strata. It homogenises experiences and contexts across women of different hues and does not delve deeper into women's life experiences. Much of the discourse has counted women as beneficiaries rather than participants of development without exploring the role of the complex socio-political, cultural, and economic dynamics that they live through every day of their lives. This is also connected with the assumption of knower (producer) and non-knower (consumer) of knowledge in the context of women. For instance, women contribute a larger share of work participation in the agriculture sector.

Women make significant contributions to agricultural and rural economies across the world, particularly in developing countries (Boserup, 1970, 1975, Boserup et al., 2007) where women represent approximately 43 per cent of the agricultural labour force. Women's work includes sowing and harvesting crops, caring for livestock, processing and preparing food, collecting fuel and water, engaging in trade and marketing, and caring for family members' nutritional needs. Their role is significant in agricultural production, food security and nutrition, land and natural resource management, and building resilience to climate change. "The critical role and contribution of rural women, including indigenous women, includes enhancing agricultural and rural development, improving food security, and eradicating rural poverty." (Peroni, 2017). In India, too, women are extensively engaged in agriculture and allied sectors. The workforce participation rate for rural women is significantly higher at 41.8 per cent against urban women participation rate of 35.31 per cent (MoSPI, 2017). Dalits have 12 per cent of all operational holdings and only 8.6 per cent of all total farm area as per the Agriculture Census 2015-16 (MoAFW, GoI, 2019).

As evident, Indian society is based on strong social hierarchy embedded in the historical caste system, most farming work is done by Shudra and Ati Shudra castes (Omvedt, 1995, Bakshi, 2016) and the land ownership is highly unequal among different castes (Anand, 2016). Omvedt (1995) is categorical in stating that the Shudra cultivator status was linked with a more liberal treatment of women, as compared to other upper castes. The women from peasant caste who worked in the field had important economic and managerial roles (Kade 2021). Given the resource hierarchy, the marginality in ownership of land has remained highest among the Dalit and tribal women. A larger share of population among the tribal groups and scheduled castes are landless or own small land holdings and are marginal farmers. Landlessness and marginality is highest among Dalit and tribal women farmers often experiencing oppression. Omvedt (1995) indicated that the work participation of Brahmin women in farming has been much lower as compared to that of the women belonging to the peasant castes. The participation of women in agriculture is highest among Dalit castes; more than male workers and field labourers. Clearly, women are a significant economic producer along with men.

The hierarchical structure induces power relations across men of different castes; men and women; and among women across different castes. The stark example of this is evident in the agricultural wage differentials (The Hindu, 2013). The Hindu report published in 2013 states that the wages paid to men for agricultural work such as ploughing was 70% higher than wages paid to women in 2004-05 and the difference has increased over the years rising to 93.6% in 2013-14. This is despite the fact that women across caste groups, manage 13.9% of India's total agricultural land holdings. The share, however, is marginally lower for women from Scheduled Castes (SCs) who manage 13.4% of the land operated by their communities for agriculture as evident from the Agricultural Census, 2015-16 (MoAFW, GoI, 2019).

Ruth Dixon in her book *Mobilizing Women for Rural Employment in South Asia: Issues of Class, Caste, and Patronage*. Economic Development and Cultural Change explained that the caste identity not only influences the frequency of women's work outside but also the type of work women have to do. As in the caste system, most unclean tasks or occupation had been allocated to the lower caste, the women farm labourers from lower caste are allocated those tasks that are considered as most unclean, for example tasks such as sweeping, washing, fishing, herding, etc. Socialist-feminist Maria Mies, a Marxist scholar renowned for her theory of capitalist patriarchy, which recognises third world women and difference, has vehemently argued that labour which is spent in the production of life or subsistence production, largely non-wage labour which is mainly done by women, should be defined

as work and not as ‘unconscious natural’ activity (Mies, 1999). Alexandra Kollontai, another socialist feminist subscribes that women’s rights were closely related to the rights of the working class as a whole. She argued that women were not enslaved by economic conditions alone, but also by social and psychological factors.

In the Indian context, re-imagining a reformed society is necessary for bringing the equal position of women in the family and society. However, the rights of Dalits, women, minorities, and labourers are violated within the caste system. For re-imagining reforms in every aspect of society, Dr BR Ambedkar’s concept of distributive justice based on a casteless society cannot be overlooked.

“If liberty means the destruction of dominion which one man holds over another then obviously it cannot be insisted upon that economic reform must be one kind of reform worthy pursuit. If the source of power and dominion is at any given time or in any given society social and religious then social reform must be accepted as the necessary sort of reform.”

- Dr. B.R. Ambedkar in *A Innihilation of Caste* (1979)

It is observed that the apathy towards gendered-consciousness is not ignorance, but an adamant commitment to patriarchy. As development outcomes become evident through a spectrum of indicators, women continue to register slower progress (Arrow, 1973; Anker and Hein, 1985) and, in some spheres, slip down the ladder of gender justice (World Bank, 2001; OECD, 2004; Appendini, 2010). Among women, Dalit women bear the larger burden in spaces within and outside the household (Bennett, 1992; Batliwala, 1993). Instead of making marginalised women objects of enquiry, the need is of a conducive environment for ensuring that they engage as the primary agents of enquiry. This is necessary because caste-based social exclusion is concomitant with deprivation and discrimination faced in spheres such as market, where buying and selling of goods, particularly home based, occurs (Thorat, et al, 2006) and engages a large section of women; education where school children from privileged and underprivileged groups are made to sit separately (Nambissan, 1996), especially during the mid-day meal time (Sabharwal, 2011; Borooah et al., 2014); and care providers, especially at the grassroots level, mostly women, are treated differently depending on their caste (Verma and Acharya, 2017). There are evidences of differential treatment meted to underprivileged populations by the privileged groups across the country (Shah et al., 2006). The Commission on Social Determinants of Health (CSDH, 2008) recognised disparities based on social identities as an important component of the social determinant framework,

and was meticulously illustrated by Nayar (2007). Others exploring from this perspective include Khandy and Akram (2012), Baah et al., (2019). Others have mostly emphasised on gender and poverty related factors (Sen, 1999; Wagstaff, 2001; Nambiar and Muralidharan, 2017). Social exclusion is attributable to historical deprivation; and barriers in access to opportunities, services and resources, more so for women because of their subordinate position in the society. It, therefore, becomes imperative to understand social exclusion of women from underprivileged groups from access to health resources, factors leading to their exclusion; and strategies to end their exclusion.

Perspective from the Data:

India is positioned very low in the Global Hunger Index (GHI) consistently for the past few years. Ranking 107 out of 121 countries in 2022 (Roy, 2022), it has slipped from its earlier position. In 2021, it ranked 101, and in 2020, the position improved to 94 from 102 out of 117 countries in 2019. In 2018, its position was 103 out of 132; and in 2017, India was at 100 out of 119 (GHI). It is noteworthy that the slipping down from her earlier position in the GHI has been consistent, but the gap is widest between 2021 and 2022. Therefore, it is important to consider the status of the marginalised groups vis-à-vis hunger and nutrition.

Evidence from the political participation suggests that the 14th Lok Sabha (Lower House) had a total of 75 elected representatives (MPs) from among the SCs, of which 65 were men and 10 were women. In the 15th Lok Sabha general election ((2009) for the 543 electoral constituencies 8070 candidates contested, of which 7514 were men and 556 were women from different social groups. Among 556 contested women, only 57 got elected. Of those who got elected, 12 women belonged to schedule caste, five were from schedule tribe, and 40 were from other groups. Lower participation and representation of women, and in particular of Dalit Women as elected representatives is starkly evident (IIDS, 2011).

In the labour force, there are more women in the agriculture sector than men. Dalit [administratively labelled as Scheduled Caste (SC)] women in the rural areas are predominantly engaged in the farm sector as agricultural labourers, while the non-scheduled community women (both among caste and tribal groups) work as cultivators. The SC women agricultural labourers are unorganised, more vulnerable with limited social security as compared to women from non-scheduled communities. In the urban areas, the majority of the SC women workforce are employed in the category of 'other workers' who are engaged in factory, plantation, trade, etc. and have negligible access to capital.

The gender gap in 2001 for SCs was 24.7 percentage points and the national average was 21.7 percentage points. The child sex ratio among Dalits declined from 938 girls per 1,000 boys in 2001 to 933 in 2011, meaning more Dalit girls were either being aborted or were dying due to negligence. Despite a declining trend, the overall sex ratio for both SCs and STs is better than the national average of 943. For SCs, it is 945 women per 1,000 men. Among the SCs, there was an increase from 923 in 2001 to 946 in 2011 in urban areas and an increase from 939 to 945 in rural areas.

As regards literacy among Dalit women, only 15.6% of scheduled castes have primary education, and only 2.7% are graduates. Almost 66% of the scheduled caste (SC) population is literate, against the national literacy rate of 73%. As many as 66.4 million SC men (75.1%) and 47.2 million women (56.4%) are literate (2011 census). The literacy rate among Dalit women has increased by 14.6 percentage points—which is more than the increase for women in the general population (10 percentage points) from 2001 to 2011. The gender gap in literacy—or the difference between male and female literacy rates—of 18.7 percentage points for SCs is above the national average of 16.2 percentage points (RGI 2011).

Differential Access to Basic Healthcare Facilities:

As regards health indicators, it is evident from the NFHS-4 data that in India, Adivasis (or STs) and Dalits (SCs) are the social categories who are most deprived of basic healthcare facilities. The SCs and the STs have to travel longer to reach a healthcare facility, and most of them are not able to meet the provider as compared to the 'Others'. It is also evident that distance has become more obstructive in accessing care over the period of time across social groups. But it has been a biggest deterrent for the women from among the STs, followed by the SCs, as compared to the other two. Similarly, when providers are not available, it affects the ST women most adversely (Table 2).

Table 2 - Distance to Facility and Availability of Providers

Social groups	Distance to the health facility					No provider available						
	NFHS 3	Diff	NFHS 4	Diff	NFHS 5	Diff	NFHS 3	Diff	NFHS 4	Diff	NFHS 5	Diff
Scheduled Caste	27.3	18.5	32.5	8.3	24.3	4.9	23.9	5.7	46.3	4.3	39.5	3.4
Scheduled Tribe	44.0	35.5	42.0	17.8	33.7	14.3	35.2	17.0	54.9	12.9	50.4	14.3
Other Backward castes	26.0	17.5	29.4	5.2	22.5	3.1	23.2	5.0	43.9	1.9	38.4	2.3
Others	8.5	00	24.2	00	19.4	00	18.2	00	42.0	00	36.1	00
Don't Know	--	--	38.5	--	31.2	--	--	--	45.8	--	43.9	--
Total	--	--	29.9	--	23.2	--	--	--	44.9	--	39.2	--

Note: Diff = Absolute difference between 'Others' and Other social groups in each NFHS Round (calculated by the Author); NFHS 3 =2005-06; NFHS4=2015-16, NFHS 5=2019-2020.

Source: IIPS and ICF 2017, 2021.

Life expectancy has been a large and persistent issue across social groups (Gupta and Sudharsanan, 2022). While women have better longevity, among women, the Dalit women appear to be the worst off, with 66.31 years followed very closely by the ST women (66.89 years). The most privileged caste group (Others) has women living up to nearly 70 years, nearly four years longer than women from the scheduled communities, both castes and tribes (Table 3).

Table 3 - Life Expectancy Across Social Groups and Gender

Social Groups	Total	Male	Female
Scheduled Caste	63.13	60.32	66.31
Scheduled Tribe	64.02	60.53	66.89
Other Backward Castes	65.06	62.88	67.47
Others	67.94	66.90	69.95

Note: (at <01 year age) | Source: NFHS 4 IIPS and ICF, 2017

This is corroborated with the differential lifespan of women from Dalit groups as compared to Others. Dalit women live 14.6 years less than high caste women. The average average age at death is 39.5 years for SC women and 54.1 years for high caste (Other). Dalit women live 14.6 years lesser than high caste (Others) women (Borooah et al., 2010).

It is important to note that 70 per cent women from the privileged groups, in comparison to less than half the women from the underprivileged groups, were provided Antenatal Care (ANC) services. In addition, about one fourth of the ST and ST women received ANC from the nursing staff, ANMs, Traditional Birth Attendants (TBAs) or Lady Health Visitors (LHVs), while only 15 per cent of the privileged women were attended by these subordinate staff for ANC services. Even for the other services like protection against neonatal tetanus, weighing, and abdominal examination, and giving them iron folic tablets, all were better provided to the women from the privileged groups as compared to the SCs and the STs. Despite the progress in the access to these services, this gap is stubbornly visible continuously despite the government initiatives of providing these services in mission mode (Table 4).

Table 4 - ANC Providers and Services Received

Background characteristic	ANC provided by Doctor	ANC provided by ANM/ nurse/ midwife/ LHV	Had Birth protected against neonatal tetanus	Women weighed	Abdomen examined	Received IFA
Scheduled caste	54.6	23.0	88.8	89.1	87.2	78
Scheduled tribe	47.9	24.9	85.9	93.8	85.6	78.4
Other backward class	57.2	21.1	88.6	88.4	88.3	75.5
Other	70.3	15.4	91.3	93.6	91.4	81.3
Don't Know	57.8	15.6	86.1	91.8	83.5	73.7
Total		20.4	89.0	90.5	88.6	77.7

Source: Table 8.7 Components of antenatal care Among women age 15-49 with a live birth in the five years preceding the survey, percentages who were given or purchased iron and folic acid (IFA) tablets or syrup, took IFA for 100 days or more, received two or more tetanus toxoid (TT) injections during the pregnancy, whose birth was protected against neonatal tetanus, and who took a drug for intestinal parasites during the pregnancy for their most recent live birth, by background characteristics, India, 2015-16.

Similar observations are evident from the data on postnatal care (PNC) for mother and the new-born. While 40% of SC women and about 18% of their children; and about 33% of ST women and 13% of their children, as compared to the 42% OBC women and 18% of the children and 52% of privileged women (Others) and 21% of their children received PNC from the doctors (Table 5).

Table 5 - Doctor Provided for PNC for Mother and Newborn

Background characteristic	Doctor for Mother	Doctor for Newborn
Scheduled caste	40.3	17.7
Scheduled tribe	33.4	13.3
Other backward class	41.8	18.0
Other	51.7	20.9
Don't know	39.1	24.4
Total	43.0	18.1

Source: Table 8.22 Type of provider of first postnatal check for the mother. IIPS and ICF, 2017

Place of Delivery and Assistance Provider during Delivery:

Care during childbirth is an important indicator which reflects on the status of health services as well as the socio-economic propensity of the population groups and the ethno-cultural context in which their people may be embedded. A little of half the women aged 15-49 years among Dalits (or SCs) have delivered in the presence of a doctor in the last five years. The remaining 47.3% have delivered a live birth at home in the presence of relatives, if in the institution, then in the presence of the subordinate staff. In contrast, 66.8% of privileged women had a live birth in the presence of a doctor in the last five years.

Similarly, more than 60% per cent of SC women as compared to 46% privileged women delivered in public sector health institutions. As against this, in the private sector health care institutions, more privileged caste (Others) women (36.1% percent) delivered in the private sector in comparison to about 18 per cent of the SC and only 11 per cent of the ST women. Assistance during delivery provided by the doctors was also tilted in favour of the women from the privileged communities (Others); and those provided by the ANM or nurse or midwife or LHV were in favour of the underprivileged women from SC and ST population groups (Table 6).

Table 6 - Place of delivery and Assistance Provider during Delivery

Background characteristic by Social Groups	Place of Delivery				Assistance during Delivery by	
	Public Sector	NGO/ Trust	Private Sector	Own/ other/ Parent's Home	Doctor	ANM / nurse / midwife/LHV
Scheduled caste	59.9	0.4	18.1	23.8	52.2	27.8
Scheduled tribe	55.9	0.4	11.6	32.1	44.8	25.8
Other backward class	50.4	0.5	28.9	19.9	54.9	26.4
Other	46.1	0.7	36.1	15.6	66.8	18.4
Don't Know	54.7	0.4	18.5	22.0	57.3	19.8
Total	52.1	0.5	26.3	20.9	56.0	24.7

Source: Table 8.13 per cent distribution of live births to women aged 15-49 in the five years preceding the survey by place of delivery, and percentage delivered in a health facility, according to background characteristics, India, 2015-16; and Table 8.19 Assistance during Delivery. IIPS and ICF, 2017.

Thus, the foregoing analysis of large-scale data informs about the gender differentials as well as the disparities across women from privileged and underprivileged groups. In fact, that the health status of the Dalit women is appalling, does not deter them from constituting 11 per cent of the share of those who provide assistance during delivery (Fig 2).

Figure 1 - Assistance Provided during Delivery (in%)

Note: Per cent distribution of births in the five years preceding the survey

Source: IIPS and ICF, 2017

The Traditional Birth Attendants (TBAs) are an indispensable link in the care providing machinery of the health system. Paradoxically, they are the ones who reach the remote part of the country, where the other elements, human and non-human, fail to reach. Their contribution is immense and goes unrecognised, often ridiculed for their illiteracy and lack of 'formal' training. Their traditional knowledge acquired through generations is denigrated and instead of assimilation, external knowledge is imposed on them. These processes often undermine their knowledge, and need to be honed for better supply of care to the needy in the areas where the conventional system is unable to reach.

Conclusion:

Marginality comes in many forms and impacts women in different ways, often accentuating their vulnerabilities. Women's marginality has often been seen in context of their homogeneity. While some women are pushed to the margins, others remain at the core. Therefore, recognising women as 'knower' and as users of knowledge calls for the recognition of this

distinction. The notion of ideas and knowledge is central to women and their health and related movements. The discourse on women consolidated itself through the late 1980s and 1990s with the understanding of cultural feminism and post structuralism. As a result, women were studied from the perspective of intersectionality rather than a consolidated entity. Their contribution to the economy, particularly agriculture, paved way to recognising them in their role in social development, too. The international agencies like the UN called for the slogan, “If you educate a man, you educate one person. If you educate a woman, you educate a nation.” It’s an oft-heard quote in development circles. Women with knowledge are more likely to add to the family income by participating in the labour market, boosting the economy and accumulation of wealth for the household and the community at large. There are differential propensities for women to contribute thus. Nevertheless, those in the margins engage in arduous labour with lesser remuneration as compared to those at the core. All of this impacts their differential access to resources which enhance their health and wellbeing. Evidence is abundant from a number of data sets, especially the widely acclaimed National Family Health Surveys, which highlight the differentials across gender and between women of different hues socially, economically, and regionally. Therefore, it is imperative to recognise women’s marginality in general as compared to men; and among women, across the axes of caste, ethnicity, and religion. Only then can the policy outcome can take the desired shape.

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